
Analysis of Regional Government Bureaucracy Reform Achievements (Study at the Department of Public Housing, Settlement and Land Areas Bekasi Regency)

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ABSTRACT: Bureaucratic reform is carried out in an effort to create a government that is clean, effective and competitive and capable of encouraging national and regional development achievements, global competitiveness and improving public services, so that it can provide the best service to the community quickly, precisely, professionally, and free from collusive practices, corruption and nepotism

Bearing in mind that Bureaucratic Reform is included in the national priority agenda, through the implementation of the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map, this can support the acceleration of national and regional development. So, with the new Bureaucratic Reform strategy, it is hoped that it can also accelerate the achievement of the strategic targets of Bureaucratic Reform and have a direct impact on society.

The ever-changing environmental dynamics and increasing demands of society have also triggered the implementation of Bureaucratic Reform to become more adaptive and agile. The establishment of a Road Map for Bureaucratic Reform also aims to answer this by focusing on four aspects, namely: setting goals and targets, focusing on upstream strategic issues through the implementation of Bureaucratic Reform General and downstream strategic issues through implementing Bureaucratic Reform Thematic, as well as implementing Bureaucratic Reform General and Bureaucratic Reform Thematic at the Public Housing Service for Settlement and Land Areas in Bekasi Regency. The General Reform score for the Public Housing, Settlement and Land Areas of Bekasi Regency was 74.5 points out of a total of 100 points and Thematic Bureaucratic Reform was 16 points out of a total of 20 points. The maximum total points from the General and Thematic Reform assessment results was 120.

KEYWORDS: Achievements in The Implementation and Bureaucratic Reform

I. INTRODUCTION

Bureaucratic reform is basically an effort to improve bureaucratic performance, by improving the quality of regulations, increasing efficiency, effectiveness and accountability in all aspects of government administration and improving the quality of services to the community, which in turn will increase public trust in the Government and improve Indonesia's image in international eyes. This understanding seems very easy to understand, but it contains the complexity of a complex change process. Change is not just a change to the organizational structure, but also involves various government administration processes in all regions; harmonization and streamlining of various regulations, changes to the human resource management system that are able to encourage organizational performance; and changes to the monitoring and accountability system that is able to encourage the administration of a government that is clean and free from Corruption, Collusion and Nepotism. It is hoped that these change steps will have a positive impact on efforts to improve the quality of public services as well as changes in the mindset and work culture of the apparatus. Starting from these conditions, the government Central and regional governments need to immediately carry out reforms bureaucracy which is not only at the level of commitment but also compared in real life.¹

All of these aspects cannot stand alone, but are interrelated with each other. Changes in one aspect will have a causal influence on other aspects. Therefore, Bureaucratic Reform is not as easy as turning the palm of your hand. Bureaucratic reform requires a long time, a lot of money, as well as consistency, patience, never giving up and great sacrifice from the perpetrators. Thus, the Bureaucratic Reform approach taken must be a systematic, structured, gradual approach, where one stage must produce output that has a strengthening impact on changes in the next stage.

¹ Pramusinto, Agus dan Agus Purwanto, Erwan. 2009. *Bureaucratic Reform, Leadership and Public Service*. Yogyakarta: Gava Media. Page 110

Analysis of Regional Government Bureaucracy Reform Achievements (Study at the Department of Public Housing, Settlement and Land Areas Bekasi Regency)

The implementation of bureaucratic reform in Bekasi Regency begins with Bekasi Regent Regulation Number 73 of 2018 concerning the Road Map for Bekasi Regency Bureaucratic Reform 2019-2023. The technical implementation of the preparation of the Road Map for Bureaucratic Reform is divided into working groups, namely working groups I, led by the Government Assistant, to prepare action plans for structuring statutory regulations, structuring apparatus resources, strengthening supervision and strengthening performance accountability. Working Group II, led by the Assistant for Economy and Development, prepares a Change Management action plan, while Working Group III, led by the Assistant for General Administration, prepares a performance action plan for structuring and strengthening the organization, structuring management and improving the quality of public services.

In era democratization, dilemma in the relationship between the translation of democratic values and the reality of bureaucratic organizational management in society has become complicated, complicated and problematic² where in the operational process tends to be considered less flexible and less efficient. Even though this is a fact A bureaucratic system is needed in the operationalization process state administration so that it runs in accordance with predetermined rules. Bureaucracy is not a phenomenon the new one. Because it's actually a simple form has existed and been known for thousands of years.

Referring to the Regulation of the Minister for Empowerment of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2023, it is stated that "Based on the results of the evaluation of the implementation of the RB, it still shows that there is a gap between the current conditions of achievement and the conditions expected at the end of 2025. This gap can be seen from two sides, namely from the planning side and the implementation side. On the planning side, the context of the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map 2020-2024 which is stipulated in the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation Number 25 of 2020, has not yet optimally accelerated government governance which encourages accelerated achievement of national development and increased global competitiveness. In terms of implementation, the management of Bureaucratic Reform at the national and institutional levels has not been optimally perceived by the public, for example regarding concrete performance for the community, public services, and reducing the practice of Corruption, Collusion, Nepotism. The planning and implementation of Bureaucratic Reform is also still carried out partially by each Government Agency so that it has not yet focused on national strategic issues and the direction of National Development.

The achievements of the Bekasi Regency bureaucratic reform index from 2020 to 2022 according to West Java Governor Regulation Number 26 of 2023 concerning the West Java Provincial Government Bureaucratic Reform Road Map for 2023.2026 are as follows:

Table Achievements of the Bekasi Regency Government Bureaucratic Reform Index Years 2020 to 2022

Year	Bureaucratic Reform Index
2020	59,66
2021	58,33
2022	59 83

Source: West Java Governor Regulation Number 26 of 2023 concerning West Java Provincial Government Bureaucratic Reform Road Map for 2023.2026.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach. This method was chosen because the problems studied are very complex, dynamic and full of meaning so they cannot be captured using quantitative research methods. Apart from that, the use of qualitative methods is intended to understand in depth the issue of bureaucratic reform, how it is implemented, and what factors are obstacles, in order to then find steps or strategies for efforts to accelerate transformational change. Data collection was carried out using in-depth interview techniques with a number of informants who met previously established criteria.

The selection of informants as data sources in this research is based on the principle of subjects who master the problem, have data, and are willing to provide complete and accurate information, therefore those considered most appropriate to be informants in this research are employees of the District Public Housing, Settlement and Land Services Department Bekasi Regency. The data collection techniques used are interviews, observation and documentation

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Framework for Implementing Bureaucratic Reform in Bekasi Regency

The policy direction for implementing Bureaucratic Reform in Bekasi Regency is focused on improving governance management (General Bureaucratic Reform) and accelerating the implementation of the development agenda which is capable of resolving public problems so that it has a real impact on society (Thematic Bureaucratic Reform). The acceleration of various development agendas that have a real impact on society must of course be pursued through improving governance. Therefore, the development of general

² Pfiffner, John M. & Robert v Presthus. 1962, *Public Administration*. New York: the Ronald press

Analysis of Regional Government Bureaucracy Reform Achievements (Study at the Department of Public Housing, Settlement and Land Areas Bekasi Regency)

RB and thematic bureaucratic reform are actually efforts that have a positive causal relationship and must be implemented in an integrated and simultaneous manner.

Picture. Framework Implementasi Reformasi Birokrasi di Kabupaten Bekasi

B. Management of Regional Government Bureaucratic Reform

To ensure effectiveness and efficiency in implementing bureaucratic reform policies in West Java, both general bureaucratic reform and thematic bureaucratic reform require integration in their development. This integration is sought by improving the management of Bureaucratic Reform within the Regional Government of West Java Province. In contrast to the previous periodization of the West Java Bureaucratic Reform Roadmap, the bureaucratic reform management was formed in a Bureaucratic Reform Team with a fairly large number of members which from the evaluation results was deemed not optimal, so in the 2022-2027 West Java Bureaucratic Reform Roadmap the Bureaucratic Reform Management at the Regional Government level is arranged in a structured manner. simpler with a fairly clear and directed division of roles.

To ensure effectiveness and efficiency in implementing bureaucratic reform policies in West Java, which are technically operational and carried out by regional officials, it is necessary to form a Bureaucratic Reform Manager within the scope of regional apparatus. The manager of bureaucratic reform at the regional level is called the Project Transformation Unit (PTU).

Picture. Management of Bureaucratic Reform at Regional Level

1. Focus of Strategy for Implementing Bureaucratic Reform at the Public Housing Service for Settlement and Land Areas in Bekasi Regency

Guarantee that there will be continuity of improvements that have been made (continuous improvement) in the implementation of Bureaucratic Reform in Bekasi Regency, along with changes in policies for implementing Bureaucratic Reform through sharpening the 2020-2024 national Bureaucratic Reform roadmap, the implementation of the evaluation of the Implementation of Bureaucratic Reform at the regional level will be the focus strategy in implementing Bureaucratic Reform in Bekasi Regency. The implementation

Analysis of Regional Government Bureaucracy Reform Achievements (Study at the Department of Public Housing, Settlement and Land Areas Bekasi Regency)

of bureaucratic reform in regional apparatus is generally divided into 2 components, namely the Implementation of General Bureaucratic Reform and the Implementation of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform as follows:

a) Implementation of General Bureaucratic Reform at the Public Housing Service for Settlement and Land Areas in Bekasi Regency

The implementation of General Bureaucratic Reform at the Public Housing Service for Settlement Areas and Bekasi Regency is an internalization strategy for the implementation of General Bureaucratic Reform at the regional government level with the aim of accelerating the achievement of performance in implementing bureaucratic reform at the regional government level. By involving all regional apparatus, it is hoped that implementation can be carried out more quickly. In addition, by implementing General Bureaucratic Reform, it is hoped that government governance at the regional level can be measured and evaluated so as to provide data and information for improvements, when obstacles occur in implementing bureaucratic reform. Implementation of General Bureaucratic Reform for the Bekasi Regency Public Housing and Land Area Service refers to the targets and indicators for the implementation of General Bureaucratic Reform at the Regional Government level, with scope limitations at the regional apparatus level. The targets and indicators for the Implementation of General Bureaucratic Reform for the Bekasi Regency Public Housing and Land Areas Service are as follows:

Table Achievements in the Implementation of General Bureaucratic Reform

Assessment Indicators	Bureaucratic Reform Score
Strategic Achievement (50)	
Effective and Collaborative Digital Governance	27,3
Moral Bureaucratic Culture	11
Amount	38,3
Moral Bureaucratic Culture (40)	
Maturity level of the Government's internal control system	7,2
Level of Follow-up on Community Submissions	5
Assess the Quality of Public Policy	4
The Value of Legal Reform	4
Value of Goods and Services Procurement Governance	4
Apparatus Professional Index	4
Amount	28,2
Achievements of the General Bureaucratic Reform Strategy (10)	
General Bureaucratic Reform Action Plan	4
Level of Implementation of the General Bureaucratic Reform Action Plan	4
Amount	8
Total Achievements of General Bureaucratic Reform	74,5

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

The results of the analysis of the achievements of the General Bureaucratic Reform of the Bekasi Regency Public Housing, Settlement and Land Area Service are divided into three indicators. The first indicator is Strategic Achievement with a maximum weight of (50). The Bureaucratic Reform Achievement of the Strategic Achievement indicator is 38.3, resulting from the Effective and Collaborative Digital Governance sub-indicator of 27.3 and the Moral Bureaucratic Culture sub-indicator of 11.

Second, the achievement of the Moral Bureaucratic Culture indicator is 28.2 weights (40). Achievements of Bureaucratic Reform Moral Bureaucratic Culture are produced through the sub-indicators Maturity level of the Government's internal control system with a value of 7.2, Level of Follow-up on Community Submissions with a value of 5, Assess the Quality of Public Policy with a value of 4, The Value of Legal Reform with a score of 4, Value of Goods and Services Procurement Governance with a score of 4 and Apparatus Professional Index with a score of 4.

The third achievement of the Achievements of the General Bureaucratic Reform Strategy indicator is a value of 8 from the weight (10) which is produced through the General Bureaucratic Reform Action Plan sub-indicator with a value of 4 and the Level of Implementation of the General Bureaucratic Reform Action Plan sub-indicator with a value of 4. The overall achievement of the General Bureaucratic Reform of the Bekasi Regency Public Housing, Settlement and Land Area Service is 74.5 points out of weight (100) in the Good (B) category.

Analysis of Regional Government Bureaucracy Reform Achievements (Study at the Department of Public Housing, Settlement and Land Areas Bekasi Regency)

b) Implementation of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform for Regional Apparatus

Implementation of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform in regional apparatus is a strategy to measure the extent to which improvements in government governance in regional apparatus have a positive correlation with resolving development issues in accordance with the core business of the regional apparatus (impact). The implementation of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform at the Bekasi Regency Public Housing, Settlement and Land Area Service refers to the targets and indicators for the implementation of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform at the Regional Government level, with scope limitations at the regional apparatus level. The targets and indicators for the Implementation of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform for Regional Apparatus are as shown in Table as follows:

Table Achievements in the Implementation of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform

Assessment Indicators	Bureaucratic Reform Score
Strategy for Building Thematic Bureaucratic Reform	
Thematic Bureaucratic Reform Development Action Plan	4
Level of Implementation of the Thematic Bureaucratic Reform Development Action Plan	4
Amount	8
Impact Achievements of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform (10)	
Impact Achievements of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform	8
Amount	8
Total Achievements of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform	16

Source: Data Processing Results, 2024

The results of the analysis of the achievements of the Thematic Bureaucratic Reform of the Bekasi Regency Public Housing and Land Area Service are 16 out of the total weight (20) or good category (B). Achievements of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform are produced from 2 indicators, namely the first indicator is the Strategy for Building Thematic Bureaucratic Reform with the Thematic Bureaucratic Reform Development Action Plan sub-indicator with a value of 8 and the Level of Implementation of the Thematic Bureaucratic Reform Development Action Plan sub-indicator of 8. Meanwhile the indicators the second is Impact Achievements of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform with an achievement score of 8.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion and data processing, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Bureaucratic reform is carried out in an effort to create a government that is clean, effective and competitive and capable of encouraging national and regional development achievements, global competitiveness and improving public services, so that it can provide the best service to the community quickly, precisely, professionally, and free from collusion practices. Corruption and Nepotism. Bearing in mind that Bureaucratic Reform is included in the national priority agenda, through the implementation of the Bureaucratic Reform Road Map, this can support the acceleration of national and regional development. So, with the new Bureaucratic Reform strategy, it is hoped that it can also accelerate the achievement of the strategic targets of Bureaucratic Reform and have a direct impact on society.
2. The ever-changing environmental dynamics and increasing societal demands have also triggered the implementation of Bureaucratic Reform to become more adaptive and agile. The establishment of a Road Map for Bureaucratic Reform also aims to answer this by focusing on four aspects, namely: setting goals and targets, focusing on upstream strategic issues through the implementation of General Bureaucratic Reform and downstream strategic issues through the implementation of Thematic Bureaucratic Reform, as well as implementing Bureaucratic Reform General and Thematic Bureaucratic Reform in the Bekasi Regency Public Housing and Settlement Area Services. The score obtained for General Reform of the Public Housing Service for Settlement and Land Areas in Bekasi Regency was 74.5 points out of a total of 100 points and Thematic Bureaucratic Reform was 16 points out of a total of 20 points. The maximum total points from the General and Thematic Reform assessment results was 120.

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Analysis of Regional Government Bureaucracy Reform Achievements (Study at the Department of Public Housing, Settlement and Land Areas Bekasi Regency)

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